

Plant-based

Fermentation

Cultivated

The UK's alternative protein research ecosystem

Alternative proteins – plant-based, fermentation-derived or cultivated – offer a promising solution to meet the projected growth in the global demand for meat, seafood, eggs, and dairy, while building a more sustainable food system.

483 publications

#3 in publication volume in Europe
+246% from 2020 to 2025

607 patents

#5 in published patent volume in Europe

Leading research organisations

Unique publications

Total public funding

Million € · 2020-2025

Funding per capita

€ per person · 2020-2025

With the right policy support, innovative ways of producing everyday foods using fermentation could contribute significantly to the national economy by 2050.

£9.8B

annual economic contribution

£2.4B

in fermentation market